

Impact of Social Media Usage Frequency and Type on Academic Self-Efficacy in College Students

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Abstract

This study investigates how college students' academic self-efficacy and social media usage habits relate to each other. It specifically looks at the connection between students' confidence in their ability to finish academic assignments in relation to general usage frequency, and active and passive social media activity. Convenience sampling was used to select 119 college students, ages 18 to 25, who were from different majors. Two questionnaires were given to the participants via online surveys: the Academic Self-Efficacy Scale and the Social Media Activity Questionnaire (SMAQ). The data was evaluated using multiple regression, correlation analysis, and descriptive statistics. We anticipate that active use and higher frequencies of overall social media usage are negatively correlated with academic self-efficacy, passive use is positively correlated with academic self-efficacy. These results show how social media affects students' perceptions of themselves academically and suggest useful strategies for enhancing study habits and optimizing online conduct in order to achieve better academic self-efficacy.

Keywords: Self-Efficacy, Social Media, Academic Self-Efficacy, Social Media Activity

Questionnaire (SMAQ), Active Social Media Usage, Passive Social Media Usage, Academic Self-Efficacy Scale, Social Media Usage Frequency

Introduction

Social media is defined simply as websites designed for users to create or share content and then communicate in it virtually. Social media has reached a large number of users (4.2 billion) as it developed (Statista, 2021). Social media, which include platforms like Facebook, Instagram, and Twitter, now introduced a very strong component into social interaction. Although all these platforms have numerous important roles, including handling academic related activities, sharing knowledge on various types of information, and professional networking, the high frequency usage of social media raises further questions towards academic self-efficacy within college students.

Self-efficacy refers to a person's belief in the capability to mobilize the cognitive resources or skills to execute a specified behavior toward achieving an outcome (Bandura, 1977). Therefore, self-efficacy becomes critical in understanding behavior changes and outcomes with reference to the academic spheres. For self-efficacy, Bandura defines four distinct sources such as mastery experience, vicarious experience, verbal persuasion, as well as bodily or emotional states. For example, mastery experience is direct achievement that tends to produce belief in the person's capacities. Vicarious experiences are about seeing others doing things successfully, which can help generate the confidence that suggests achievement is within reach. Verbal persuasion is the form of encouragement that another creates or feedback from others by which an individual comes to believe that he can perform or achieve results. Emotional states such as anxiety or stress enter into the place for those appraisal aspects because, as a general rule, the higher emotional tension is, the lower self-efficacy tends to become. Social media platforms such as, Instagram, LinkedIn, etc., are good platforms for a vicarious experience to showcase your peers' achievements, but it may lead to negative self-comparisons and lower confidence.

Verbal persuasion through social media such as supportive comments and peer interaction may enhance self-efficacy by virtue of gaining validation from others as well as encouragement. In contrast, negative feedback or unpleasant exchanges can reduce, marking the ambivalence of social media in that respect. Emotional states are also entangled in social media use; for most, these platforms are calming or uplifters, while for some, they constitute higher waves of stress or even anxiety, owing to the internet-driven connection and perceived social pressure. Given the all-presence of social media, self-efficacy could be inferred from its multifaceted effects.

By analyzing such interactions, scholars could know how the student academic intentions and self-efficacy levels transform in the increasingly digitally influenced paradigms of interactions through the Internet. Thus, influence on these sources must merit rigorous criticism. Prior studies have claimed that social media has both a positive and a negative effect on the academic performance of students. Some studies concluded that social media would still serve as a platform for academic collaboration and sharing knowledge in the transformation of valuable grades. For example, WhatsApp plays roles in initiating group discussion, project activities, and overall academic engagement contributing positively towards academic self-efficacy (Boahene et al., 2019). In contrast, excessive use of social media, especially passive scrolling activities, comparison of statuses, and so on, has been shown to produce adverse psychological outcomes such as low self-efficacy and anxiety (Krasnova et al. 2013). Active usage refers to engagement like content creation, commenting, and substantive engagement and passive usage—such as scrolling through feeds without destination—often corresponds with social comparison and lower self-esteem. Ahmad and Jan (2017) proved that the mode of involvement that involves passively being present on Facebook has negative self-appraisals, primarily because of upward social comparisons, likely to undermine academic confidence.

As previously said, the effect of social media on self-efficacy varies nuancedly among different demographic groups. For example, Zucker and Light (2013) found that the specific types of digital technology kinds, such as using email and playing educational games, can have positively queering effects for students with low socioeconomic status on academic self-efficacy and general self-efficacy; however, the use of social networking was negatively related to academic self-efficacy. Differentiating between types of engagement makes it apparent that there is truly something one way or another. In the case of older adults, higher levels of self-efficacy for social media (SMSE), according to Chen and Gao (2022), were shown to enable productive use of social media and to lower the feelings of loneliness and self-esteem. Although their conclusions include older individuals alone, they indicate or may imply a wider psychological effect from social media self-efficacy to include impacts on younger users, even college students.

Prior research leaves many questions unanswered because of the several aspects of investigation that remain unfilled in the relationship between patterns of using social media and academic self-efficacy. Most previous research attention had been on the consequence of social media on mental health appraised broadly for example depression and anxiety, not specifically on academic outcomes. Also deficient was the active versus passive use of social media. This study aims to fill these gaps by exploring associations between frequency and type of social media use (active vs. passive) and academic self-efficacy among college students.

The research question concerning the study is: “Is the relationship between the frequency of social media usage and the way it is being used negatively related to college students’ academic self-efficacy?,” the question aims to look at the dynamic relationship between academic self-efficacy and social media usage. It is hoped that from the findings, an understanding could

emerge on how best social media can be utilized in helping, rather than obstructing, learning success.

Materials and Method

Research Design

The research model and variables identified in this study include independent variables that measure the frequency of usage (daily screen time) and the two levels of social media engagement (passive and active). The dependent variable is academic self-efficacy, which is determined by how confident a person is in their capacity to finish academic tasks including assignments, study, and test-taking. An electronic survey with demographic and academic self-efficacy and social media participation measures was administered to participants as part of a between-subjects design. Without trying to examine the connection between social media use and self-efficacy, this enables one to examine the distinctions between active and passive users. A survey conducted online was used to administer the test. The association between academic self-efficacy and social media use patterns was investigated using a between-subjects approach.

Variables in Research

- Independent Variables:
 1. Frequency of Social Media Usage: The amount of time spent on social media platforms on average within hours.
 2. Type of Social Media Usage:
 - (i) Active Usage: Engaging with other users such as liking, commenting, and actively posting.
 - (ii) Passive Usage: Simply scrolling through without any engagement.

Participants

119 Bilkent University students volunteered for the study. The sample size was set as 119, to which it was concluded that with average statistical power (commonly 0.80) and significance levels ($p < 0.05$) it would be possible to identify significant effects. These students, ranging in age from 18 to 25, were a representative cross-section of fields of study, consisting of both technical and social science programs. This type of diversity in the sample allows for a better exploration of social media use patterns and their potential effects on academic self-efficacy. Recruitment of the participants was done by convenience sampling. This was used to get as many responses as there is time and resources for. Students were accessed through the internal email system of the university (BAIS) as well as popular social media such as WhatsApp, Instagram, and X (formerly Twitter). Using more than one platform helped reach a wide audience and ensured a better opportunity for having a representative and diverse sample. To encourage participation, students were informed that they would receive five GE250/251 points for completing the survey

In order to enhance the overallizability of the findings, the sample included students from different years of study and levels of social media usage. This was carried out in order to capture a wide variety of social media usage behavior, which reflects the real-world variability present among the student population of the university. Through the inclusion of students from different majors, ranging from natural science and engineering to social sciences and humanities, the study aimed at neutralizing the danger of sampling bias and extending the relevance of the findings into a broader academic framework.

The data collection was methodically conceived so as not to violate ethical issues and erode privacy on the side of participants. Before they underwent the survey, they were presented with an informed consent form indicating the aim of the study, potential risks, and voluntary involvement. They were promised that their responses would be kept confidential and only utilized for research in an academic environment. In addition, the survey link was sent via several channels to ensure that students who may not regularly use one particular platform would not be excluded. In order to maintain ethical guidelines, the participants were told that taking part would not affect their academic standing or be utilized for any type of personal assessment. The researchers went to great lengths to ensure that participation was entirely voluntary and that respondents had the ability to leave at any point without consequence. Having such an open policy not only adhered to ethical research but also helped create a sense of trust, which ensured honest and cautious responses.

Procedure

Participants first got a consent form. Whenever they decide to move on, demographic information was collected, such as age, sex, college major and year, and length of schooling.

Respondents then be asked how many hours a day on average they spend on social media platforms. Through the settings on their phones or social media accounts, individuals were prompted to self-report how much time they spend on screens on average. Following that, students filled out the Social Media-Activity Questionnaire (SMAQ), which collects data on their social media usage and role (passive or active). Using a 5-point Likert-

type scale (1 = Never, 5 = Very Often), participants used self-report to report their active behaviors, such as commenting and interacting. The Academic Self-Efficacy Scale, a self-reported, standardized questionnaire designed to assess an individual's confidence in their capacity to conduct a variety of academic-related tasks, including studying, finishing assignments, and taking tests, was given to participants in the study's subsequent phase. Additionally, a 5-point Likert scale was used to rate it. Participants could see a link to another form requesting their name, last name, and Bilkent ID number after completing the questionnaire. The information gathered from the form and the surveys was not combined. The participants remain anonymous in this kind of way. Lastly, the individuals were categorized in order to facilitate analysis. Users of social media were categorized as either active or passive based on the sort of activity they engage in, and their academic self-efficacy ratings were analyzed in connection with the forms of social media they use. All procedures were conducted online, which is advantageous because it ensures participant privacy and convenience. Every participant shall finish every task, however in order to prevent the order effect, the tasks were completed in a random sequence. Initially, half of the participants completed the Academic Self-Efficacy Scale, while the other half completed the SMAQ. The test consists of questions that are similar or identical yet have slightly different wording. In this fashion, we can ensure that participants are reading the questions and answering them correctly rather than randomly. Not every question on the test is favorably formulated, and there were attention-check questions like "Please select 'Strongly Agree' for this question." For instance, a person who consistently selects option 5 for each test question will not provide consistent responses. We were able to detect those who are not totally engaged in this way.

Materials and Measures:

Academic Efficacy Scale

Abdul Gafoor K. and P. Muhammed Ashraf standardized the Academic Self-Efficacy Scale in 2006 as a standardized instrument for assessing students' confidence in their capacity to complete specific academic assignments. This measure, which emphasizes confidence in one's capacity to accomplish desired results, is derived from Bandura's Self-Efficacy Theory. Its simple Likert-scale style enables effective data collection and analysis, and it is a broad scale of academic skills and behaviors that may be tailored for various educational levels and cultural contexts. The scale assesses the students' academic self-efficacy, or their confidence in their capacity to do academic activities including studying, time management, and test-taking. Although it was first created for secondary school students in consideration, the products' content is appropriate for university students as well, thus it may be utilized for students at different educational levels. 20 positive statements, like "I can arrange help from my teachers when needed," and 20 negative statements, like "I cannot manage time efficiently for learning," make up the scale's 40 items. The scale measures a number of aspects of academic self-efficacy, including goal orientation, learning process, reading and comprehension, memory, time management, peer and teacher relationships, exam preparation and performance, and resource usage. A 5-point Likert scale is used for responses, with 1 denoting "Exactly False," 2 "Nearly False," 3 "Neutral," 4 "Nearly True," and 5 "Exactly True." Negative statements receive a reverse score, whilst positive ones receive a direct score. Greater academic self-efficacy is indicated by higher scores. It has been observed that the academic self-efficacy scale has a test-retest coefficient greater than 0.85, indicating consistent assessments throughout time.

Social media-activity questionnaire (SMAQ)

SMAQ is a valid, standardized, and trustworthy instrument for assessing social media use. The Facebook Active and Watching scale of the Facebook Activity Questionnaire served as the basis for the development of the items in SMAQ (Ozimek & Bierhoff, 2016). On a 5-point Likert-type scale, with 1 denoting never and 5 denoting very often, it consists of eight active items, such as "I post images," and eleven passive ones, such as "I peek at the "newsfeed" to see the latest activity of other users (e.g., if they have new friends). Posting and communicating with others are examples of active behaviors. Reading comments or scrolling are examples of passive activities, which include ingesting content without actively participating. SMAQ exhibits strong dependability over time, as seen by its test-retest reliability coefficient of 0.94.

Results

The results derived from the analyses of data presented several important trends with regard to social media usage patterns and academic self-efficacy among university students. As such, main testing was undertaken in terms of passive use, active use, and total time spent on social media.

Passive Social Media Use:

In terms of correlation, there is a significant negative relationship between passive social media use and academic self-efficacy ($r = -0.219$, $p = 0.017$), which indicates that students who stay on social media for more time engaging in passive behaviors such as scrolling down one page after another without ever interacting with content give themselves lower grades in terms of confidence regarding their academic aptitudes. In the linear regression model, since $\beta = -0.128$, $p = 0.034$, passive social media use predicted lower academic self-efficacy.

Active Social Media Use:

The scenario obtained was that no relationship exists between active use and academic self-efficacy ($r = 0.012$, $p = 0.893$), implying that social engagement in posting, commenting, or any other forms of communication does not seem to influence students' perceptions of their academic ability. The linear regression also confirmed no significant association existing in the relationship ($\beta=0.047$, $p=0.203$).

Total Time Spent on Social Media:

Even though the greater time spent on social media causes a slight negative effect, the association with academic self-efficacy is not statistically significant ($r=-0.143$, $p=0.123$). Regression analysis supported this with non-significant values for prediction ($\beta=-0.007$, $p=0.803$).

Figure 3. Scatterplot showing the relationship between time spent on social media and academic self-efficacy. No significant relationship is observed.

Figure 1. Scatterplot showing the relationship between passive social media use and academic self-efficacy. A negative relationship is observed.

Figure 2. Scatterplot showing the relationship between active social media use and academic self-efficacy. No significant association is observed.

Discussion

The significance of this study further underscoring the nature of social media engagements rather than merely the time spent in online interaction. This social media has become an integral part of the student's daily lives, yet the kind of social interactions that students choose may have a huge bearing on their perception of academic ability. For example, the found negative association between passive social media use and academic self-efficacy means that selling content without any form of interaction can lead to either feelings of inadequacy or an actual decrease in self-understandings in academic implications.

This fits well with past research suggesting that passive social media use, involving activities such as browsing and scrolling without interaction, can drive down individual well-being and self-perception (Verduyn et al., 2017). Use of this nature could facilitate upward social comparisons, with the unfortunate effect of students feeling less capable than their peers. And even though no significant relationship was found for active social media use and academic self-efficacy, this would counter the view that engagement would then go on to build self-confidence. It seems clear that being actively engaged in social interaction online does not necessarily and automatically translate to an enhancement of academic self-belief.

The absence of any significant relationship between total social media usage time and academic self-efficacy shows a better understanding that the quality of engagement may be more influential than quantity. This finding adds to the body of literature that demands a more sophisticated exploration of online activities rather than exclusive duration measures. Practically, it means that educational interventions aimed at minimizing negative impacts of social media on academic self-efficacy need to be targeted at how students engage with content and not on discouragement of social media use. Passive social media usage, operationalized as scrolling without active engagement, emerged as a negative predictor of academic self-efficacy.

This is in line with current literature demonstrating that passive use lowers psychological well-being (Verduyn et al., 2017).

Conversely, active use, as represented by commenting and posting, did not significantly impact academic self-efficacy. This finding contradicts certain assumptions that more interactive forms of social media use may enhance self-perception. It suggests that being more interactive on social media does not necessarily culminate in increased academic confidence. The fact that there is no strong correlation between total time spent on social media and academic self-efficacy validates the need to focus on qualitative aspects of use over simple quantity of time. It aligns with growing evidence indicating that time spent online doesn't necessarily predict well-being or academic success, but rather how time is spent.

Conclusion

Overall, the current study highlights the importance of taking into account the specific forms of social media interaction when assessing their effect on academic self-efficacy. The findings show that passive social media use, i.e., low interactivity and consumption-oriented behavior, is most likely to have a negative impact on students' belief in academic ability. Conversely, neither active social media use nor total online time had significant impacts, which suggests that spending more time or being actively involved is not necessarily jeopardizing or enhancing academic self-efficacy.

The results contribute to the literature on digital literacy and mental health in educational settings. While social media is becoming an integral part of students' lives, education about how different patterns of use influence self-perception is the most critical. The current study sheds light on the need to change the focus of policymakers and teachers from time constraints towards encouraging healthier patterns of online engagement among students. An awareness of the complexity of social media interaction can aid teachers and mental health professionals to better handle the challenges posed by online conduct in students.

Limitations & Future directions

This study has several limitations that must be considered when evaluating the findings. The first of these is the utilization of self-reported data, which necessarily involves threats to response bias of either social desirability or recall inaccuracy. Participants may have over- or underreported their usage of social media or their academic self-efficacy, and as such the findings are open to bias. In later studies, the addition of more objective measures, such as digital tracking data, can provide a better estimate of social media usage. Also, the sample populations in this study were restricted to students of a single university, and thus generalizability to broader populations was limited. Cultural context, learning environment, and organizational norms could influence the degree to which social media usage supports academic self-efficacy. Future studies should attempt to sample more representative and diverse populations, across various universities, education systems, and cultures.

Another limitation is the cross-sectional design of the research, which rules out making causal inferences. Associations were present, but the research doesn't establish if passive use of social media will lower academic self-efficacy directly or if students with lower self-efficacy are more likely to have higher passive consumption. Longitudinal or experimental designs are required to specify the directionality of these associations.

These limitations may alter the generalizability of the study so future direction on this matter would be to do similar research on the academic self efficacy in regards to the limitations mentioned. To overcome the explained limitations, future research should take into account the following:

- Increase the sample to include students with diverse educational and cultural backgrounds to increase the external validity of findings.
- Carry out longitudinal research to establish causal relationships and examine temporal variations in social media usage patterns.
- Use a combination of objective data monitoring and self-reporting measures to yield

more precise measurement of social media usage.

- Investigate possible moderating or mediating variables, such as stress, coping style, and workload, to explore the variables underlying the interaction between social media use and academic self-efficacy.
- Investigate different types of social media content (e.g., education, entertainment, social networking) to determine whether the type of content moderates the influence on self-efficacy. Additionally, the sample consisted of only university students from a single school, thereby reducing the generalizability of the results.

References

- Ahmad, N., & Jan, M. (2017). Impact of social media on self-esteem. *European Scientific Journal*, 13(23), 329–341. <https://doi.org/10.19044/esj.2017.v13n23p329>
- Bandura, A. (1977). Self-efficacy: Toward a unifying theory of behavioral change. *Psychological Review*, 84(2), 191–215. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-295X.84.2.191>
- Boahene, K. O., Fang, J., & Sampong, F. (2019). Social media usage and tertiary students' academic performance: Examining the influences of academic self-efficacy and innovation characteristics. *Sustainability*, 11(8), 2431. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11082431>
- Chen, Y., & Gao, Q. (2022). Effects of social media self-efficacy on informational use, loneliness, and self-esteem of older adults. *International Journal of Human-Computer Interaction*, 39(5), 1121–1133. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10447318.2022.2062855>
- Gafoor, K. A., & Ashraf, P. M. (2006). Academic self-efficacy scale. University of Calicut. Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/262924154>
- Krasnova, H., Wenninger, H., Widjaja, T., & Buxmann, P. (2013). Envy on Facebook: A hidden threat to users' life satisfaction? *Wirtschaftsinformatik*, 55(6), 85–96. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11576-013-0367-0>
- Ozimek, P., & Bierhoff, H. (2016). Facebook use depending on age: The influence of social comparisons. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 61, 271–279. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2016.03.034>

Statista. (2021). Number of social media users worldwide from 2010 to 2021 (in billions). Retrieved from <https://www.statista.com/statistics/272014/global-social-networks-ranked-by-number-of-users/>

Zucker, A. A., & Light, D. (2013). Laptop programs for students. *Computers & Education*, 69, 86–96. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2013.08.018>

Appendix

Social media-activity questionnaire (SMAQ)

Scoring: each item is answered on a 1-5 scale, with the following response choices/labels: 1- Never, 2-Rarely, 3-Sometimes, 4-Often, 5-Always for "how often" items, and I-Not at all, 2, 3-Somewhat, 4, 5-Very(much) for all other items.

Item Wording

1. SMP1 I look at the photo albums of other users.
2. SMP2 I look at the profiles/pages of other users, or read through them.
3. SMP3 I look at the stories of my friends/ my subscriptions.
4. SMP4 I read private messages that other users send me.
5. SMP5 I read entries on the chronicles and personal pages of other users.
6. SMP6 I read through the comments on other users' pictures.
7. SMP8 I look at links or video clips posted on other people's profile pages (e.g., YouTube).
8. SMP9 I look at the profile pages of my relatives.
9. SMP10 I look at the "newsfeed" to see the latest activities of other users (e.g., if they have new friends).
10. SMP11* I read entries on my own chronicle.
11. SMA1 I create events or invite users to events.
12. SMA2 I post links or video clips myself.
13. SMA3 I post photos with my family.
14. SMA4 I create groups.
15. SMA5 I post photos.
16. SMA6 I respond to event invitations.
17. SMA7 I create highlights.

* deleted due to double loadings. SMP = Social Media use passive; SMA = Social Media use active.

18. SMP7 I read the comments on my own pictures.

Academic Self-Efficacy Scale

Scoring: each item is answered on a 1-5 scale, with the following response choices/labels: 1- Never, 2-Rarely, 3-Sometimes, 4-Often, 5-Always for "how often" items, and I-Not at all, 2, 3-Somewhat, 4, 5-Very(much) for all other items.

Item Wording

1. Irrespective of the subject, I am competent in learning.
2. I can not read and understand my text books well.
3. I sense that I am quick to pick the points from what I read
4. I feel that I have no ability to keep things unforgotten.
5. I can do my projects well.
6. I can't manage time efficiently for learning.
7. I can arrange the help of my teachers in learning.
8. I fail to find out the necessary sources for my study.
9. I can arrange help of my peers for my learning whenever I need it.
10. I fail to set higher goals in my study.
11. I can usually find out quite a few solutions when I confront with problems in my study.
12. I can't express ideas well while attending examinations.
13. It is difficult for me to read and understand the textbooks in English language.
14. During examinations, I can recollect what I have learnt.
15. Often I fail to comprehend the actual meaning of what I study.
16. If taught, I can prepare my class notes neatly.
17. I fail to find out time for learning in the midst of sundry chores.
18. I can't arrange the resources of my study from my relatives, neighbours, etc.
19. I am assured that I have a few friends who would be helpful in my study.
20. I may not clarify doubts from my teachers while in class, even if I reach higher classes.
21. I can accomplish my aims in learning.
22. I can't answer the essay type questions well.
23. I experience that I am weak in understanding the classes of my teachers.
24. I can develop the reading skill required to learn school subjects.
25. When I study a I can utilize the available library facility for my study.
26. I observe that I fail to prepare my seminars and assignments in time.
27. If I miss some classes for some reason, I can compensate the loss fairly well.
28. I consider that I fail to develop a healthy relationship with my teachers.
29. I am confident that I can perform well in competitive examinations.
30. I can't deal efficiently with the unexpected problems in my study.
31. I can be calm at time of exam as I am conscious of my ability to learn.
32. I can't complete the homework myself without any help from guidebooks, previous notes etc
33. I can usually handle the disturbing situations in the study.
34. If a sudden test is conducted for us without prior notice, I can answer it well.
35. If I try, I can become one of the good grade holders.
36. I can't answer the questions which teachers ask me.
37. I can score well in the short answer type questions.
38. I can't accomplish challenging tasks and problems in my study.
39. However twisted the question is I can answer them.
40. new concept, I can't recall the related knowledge from the earlier classes.

Demographic Information Form

Age:

Major:

Sex:

- Male
- Female
- Other
- Prefer not to answer

